

Means of Morphological Expression of Gradualness

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Abstract:

This article is devoted to how gradation is manifested at the morphological level. In general, the serious study of gradualness in the morphological method is of great importance in revealing the undiscovered aspects of the semantic structure of words and word forms. We have considered that gradation at the morphological level can be created with the help of three main elements.

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Introduction. The morphological method of gradualism means the gradualization of the meaning of a word using a word form or a morpheme. As we noted above, gradualness is mainly related to the object, action or event, the action itself, or the speaker's mental state and feelings.

In morphological studies, the first general views about the phenomenon of gradualness are in the representations of the level of quality, in the descriptions of categories such as three or more member possession, agreement, tense, person-number, intensification and reduction of meaning by morphological means, word groups. manifested in the transition to each other. In the course of research, it became known that the following prefixes are very active in strengthening the meanings of words related to adjectives, nouns, and verbs:

(extra-, hyper-, mega-, micro-, mini-, multi-, out-, over-, poly-, posy-, pre-, re-, en-, super-, tri-, munder-, up-, upper-, under-, un-, in-, dis-, mis-, and etc).

For example:

1. Multi-dimensional - having many different features.

Crime is a multi-dimensional problem.

2. Multilateral - involving more than two groups or countries.

Seven countries are taking part in the multilateral talks.

3. Superabundant - existing in very large amounts

Grapes and olives are superabundant in this part of France.

4. Supercharged – 1.very fast or energetic .

The economy has expanded at a supercharged pace.

2. containing or expressing very strong emotions

There was a supercharged atmosphere during the debate in the House of Commons last night.

5. *Supercilious* -behaving as if or showing that you think that you are better than other people, and that their opinions, beliefs or ideas are not important

He spoke in a haughty, supercilious voice.

6. Superfluous - more than is needed or wanted

The report was marred by a mass of superfluous detail.

7. Superhighway - a large, wide road on which traffic travels at high speed

8. Overact - to make your voice and movements express emotions too strongly when acting in a play

9. Upgrade - to improve the quality or usefulness of something, such as a machine or a computer program, or give a person a more important job or state that their job is more important than it was in the past

It's quite simple to upgrade the indexing software

10. Unacceptable - too bad to be accepted, approved of or allowed to continue

The unions have described the latest pay offer as unacceptable.

11. Polyglot - speaking or using several different languages

She was reading a polyglot bible, with the text in English, Latin and Greek.

12. Polymath - person who knows a lot about many different subjects

13. Underage - younger than the lowest age at which a particular activity is legally or usually allowed. (CALD).

Among the above prefixes, ultra-, extra- prefixes indicate the unusual strength of word meanings.

For example:

Ultrasonic -describes sound which is too high for people to hear

Extraordinarily- very; more than usual

She is, it must be said, extraordinarily beautiful.

Out-, over- these prefixes are added to adjectives, nouns, and verbs and rank the meaning of these words:

Outburst - a sudden forceful expression of emotion, especially anger

a violent outburst

Overblown - bigger or more important than it should be

an overblown news story

multi - We can see the gradualness as a result of the multi - prefix expressing the excess of the number of objects:

Multilateral - involving more than two groups or countries.

Micro-, mini- these prefixes can express gradualness, meaning that the size of objects is extremely small:

Microlight- an extremely light and small aircraft with a very small engine, which carries only one or two people

Minimal - very small in amount

There were no injuries and damage to the building was minimal.

En- prefiksi ham o'ziga xos tarzda graduallikni ifodalay oladi:

Enlarge - to become bigger or to make something bigger

They've enlarged the kitchen by building over part of the garden.

an enlarged spleen.

up-, upper-, mega- these prefixes can also contribute to the formation of the content of gradualness to a certain extent:

Upgrade - to improve the quality or usefulness of something, such as a machine or a computer program, or give a person a more important job or state that their job is more important than it was in the past

Uppermost - in the highest position or having the most importance

The office block's uppermost floors were engulfed with flames.

Megalomania - an unnaturally strong wish for power and control, or the belief that you are very much more important and powerful than you really are

Un-, in-, im-,ir-, dis-, mis- The negative meaning is strengthened in the content of graduals formed by these prefixes:

Unable - to not be able to do something

We were unable to contact him at the time.

Incomprehensible - impossible or extremely difficult to understand

These accounts are utterly incomprehensible. Can you explain them to me?

*It's incomprehensible **to** me why he would want to kill himself.*

Irresponsible - not thinking carefully enough or not worrying about what might result from actions taken

*It would be irresponsible **to** ignore these warnings.*

Impartial - not supporting any of the sides involved in an argument

impartial advice

disobey - to refuse to do something that you are told to do; to not obey

How dare you disobey me!

Mislead - to cause someone to believe something that is not true

*He has admitted misleading the police **about** his movements on the night of the murder.*

Yuqoridagilardan tashqari, -ful, -ly, -ish, ize/se, -less, -ridden, gradualness can also be created using these suffixes and up, in, on, down, postpositives:

Powerful - having a lot of power to control people and events.

Loudly- making a lot of noise.

Reddish - slightly red in colour.

Modernize - to make something more modern .

Meaningless - having no meaning.

guilt-ridden - She was guilt-ridden when she discovered that the business had failed because of her.

Build up - an increase, especially one that is gradual and steady.

Grow up - to gradually become an adult.

Put up - to raise something, or to fix something in a raised position.

Freeze up – if something freezes up, it becomes so cold that it doesn't work or cannot move= ICE UP: all the locks had frozen up;

Move in on - If you move in on a person or place, you come close or closer to them in order to attack or take control of them .

Move off sth/on(to sth) - to change from one subject to another when talking or writing.

Go down - to move down to a lower level or place or to be reduced in price, value, amount, quality, level or size.

Go on - to start talking again after a pause.

Set in - When something unpleasant sets in, it begins and seems likely to continue in a serious way

The analysis of the examples shows that morphological gradualism is well developed in noun, adjective, and verb word groups. Super-, over-, out are the most active prefixes, and -ful, -ly are among the suffixes. In our study, it was found that the prefixes un-, in-, dis-, mis-, ir-, and im- are active in showing the gradualness of words.

Conclusion. In general, the serious study of gradualness in the morphological method is of great importance in revealing the undiscovered aspects of the semantic structure of words and word forms. In this paragraph of our work, we considered that gradualism at the morphological level can be created using three main elements:

Prefixes;

Suffixes;

Postpositives.

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